

USE OF EFFECTIVE APPROACHES IN TEACHING WRITING IN NON- PHILOLOGICAL HIGHER EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS

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Abstract. *This article discusses the ability to quickly and easily memorize new words and terms that have been learned in a way that encourages students to think more while teaching English in non-linguistic higher education institutions, Writing is a way of forming and formulating thoughts in written form. Writing is an activity that it involves creative improvement of thought in a written word. It is a complex communicative activity. It helps to communicate in the written form with the help of graphical symbols*

Keywords: *writing, competence, non-philological universities, cognitive skills, tasks, method*

The written form of foreign language communication is traditionally considered by theorists and specialists as the most difficult to learn, requiring considerable effort and time. This is due to the poor preparedness of students for writing as a type of speech activity, limited study time and the priority given to oral forms of communication in the development of foreign language communicative competence. Despite this, in recent years, writing, as a type of speech activity, has begun to occupy an increasingly important place in determining the tasks of forming professional skills of intercultural communication among students of non-philological universities.

Like any other educational aspect, writing has its own goals and objectives. The main purpose of writing instruction is the formation of students' written communicative competence, which includes the possession of written signs, the content and form of a written work of speech.

The tasks to be solved in writing training are related to the creation of conditions for mastering the content of writing. These tasks include the formation of the necessary graphic automatisms in students, speech and cognitive skills and the ability to formulate thought in accordance with the written style, expanding knowledge and horizons, mastering the culture and intellectual readiness to create the content of the written work of speech, the formation of authentic ideas about the subject content, speech style and graphic form written text.

In addition, the XXI century is the century of international communication through the Internet. This type of communication includes various types and functions; therefore, various skills are developed in the lessons. Writing for teaching a foreign language plays an important role, because it reflects vocabulary, grammar skills and more. But, like all sciences, it should be interesting for students. Therefore, the teacher should properly organize the motivational moment, the interest of students.

The technology of teaching writing is considered at the stages of training, as the content of the work has its own specifics.

In order to develop the skills of reading original literature in the specialty, participate in oral communication in a foreign language in the process of training future personnel and search for information necessary for scientific purposes, English classes are held in the higher education system of the republic. A specialist in his field should be able to read the original English-language literature in his profession, understand the text read and apply it in his profession. In addition, he must be able to think freely in a foreign language with his interlocutor on a given topic.

A good effect is given by teaching English in non-philological higher educational institutions through interactive methods that allow students to further develop their thinking, receive and transmit information in English, gain new knowledge about the English language, follow scientific changes in their field and not stay up to date with the news, which expands the horizons of students. It is interesting and useful for students to work on topics that are relevant to their profession. To do this, the student must first know the meaning, pronunciation, and use of new words or terms present in the text. Interactive methods help us do this. For example, the chain drill method. The students pronounce a new word or term after hearing the sound, and pronounce a word that they have learned well, with translation, while the next student returns their word without translation and adds another word that they have learned. Thus, the game continues until the last word of the student, whose word order can help the student repeating the words to pronounce – this word only in Uzbek or Russian, so that if he cannot pronounce it, he is eliminated from the game. This game helps the student to memorize new words more easily and with interest.

The second method: the group is divided into small groups of 2 or 3 people, who insist on step and fix the settings with the game “broken Phone” (broken Phone). In this case, the student standing at the first one makes a sentence with the participation of new words and phrases and pronounces it in the ear of the student standing behind him, and he-the next student, and thus the game continues. And the WIN continues until it reaches the last student. The main task of the game is to work together with the team and strive to ensure that each student is fully aware and feels responsible for the delivery. In the process of understanding and delivering, they learn much more information. The first group that accurately conveys its opinion is considered the winner. Now it will be much easier to work with groups that have already mastered the words. The text is listened to by students through audio and tracked in writing. For the second time, the audiorecording is heard by the teacher if new words in the same text are omitted. The student must both hear and fill it out without looking at anything. The result of this practical work is checked with all students of the group and worked out for errors. Now the text is divided into groups, divided into 2 or 3 parts. Depending on the capabilities of the group, the time is determined, and they are given a task in the style of the game “translator with the speaker”, in which each of the students acts as an interpreter and speaker, that is, translates the speaker’s speech not by points, but by tones, and the speaker himself moves on to the next sentence. Processed in this way one by one. While the rest of the group will keep track of their mistakes and shortcomings and write a “feedback” (comment) to their work, telling them in English what they have understood through speech and translation. The other groups work the same way.

Moreover the word “ Syncwine “ is frantically derived from the word” five”. This is a 5-line poem, built according to the rule.

1. On the first line the subject is indicated (usually - horse).
2. The second line is a description (adjective) of the subject in two words.
3. The third line is a description of the action in the context of this topic with the help of three verbs.
4. The fourth line is a phrase consisting of four words that indicate the attitude to the subject.
5. The last line is a synonym, consisting of a word that repeats the essence of the subject.

In conclusion, we emphasize that the specificity of the proposed methodology for interconnected teaching of writing is based on a cognitive-communicative approach to mastering the language, in which a foreign language is considered as a means of communication (oral and written),

and as a means of cognition in the professional field (goals reading and processing the primary text). The cognitive-communicative approach to teaching writing opens up additional opportunities for closer integration of the “Foreign Language” discipline with the general educational disciplines of non-linguistic students and thereby increases the role of a foreign language in the formation of professional competencies.

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